

The effects of high technology export and per capita income on carbon emission: An investigation on G20 countries

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Abstract: We aim to investigate the impact of per capita income and high technology product export on CO2 emissions in G20 countries (except Russia) from 1992 to 2014 via panel data analysis. We applied random coefficient panel regression method to capture the heterogeneity of the G20 countries. The findings indicate that per capita income has stronger impact on CO2 emission level in developing countries whereas high technology export has stronger impact on CO2 emission level in developed countries. We interpret this result in the way that developing countries increase their CO2 emissions through increased income and consumption whereas developed countries do so via production and export.

JEL Classifications: F47, Q56, E01, C13

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1. Introduction

Technological development level and technological change in a country are significant determinants of economic growth. Exogenous growth models indicate that technology is not influenced by economic variables, however it has an influence on economic growth in the long run (Özel, 2012).

In today's highly competitive world, it is seen that factors such as skilled labor, technology and natural resources underlie the differences in levels of economic growth of countries. Especially, products with high technology and high added-value have importance to increase countries' performances in foreign trade (Kızılkaya et al., 2017). High technology refers to a level of technology involving a research process which requires continuous effort and therefore is characterized with the much faster regeneration of information compared to other technologies (Instituto Nacional De Estadística). Thus, the concept of high technology is used to refer to companies and industries producing goods that contain innovative qualification and advanced technologies. The common feature of such companies and industries is their possession of advanced technological and scientific expertise as well as high expenditure in research and development (Seyoum, 2004). High technology industries within the scope of manufacturing industry are aviation and spacecraft industry, pharmaceutical industry, industries producing office, accounting and information processing technologies, radio, television and communication equipment industry, and medical and optical devices industry (OECD, 2011). In this context, the production and export of high technology products pose as an important source of

finance in growth and development of countries adapting an export-oriented growth strategy by increasing export revenue (Yıldız, 2017). On the other hand, the impact of CO₂ emissions has continuously increased in parallel with increasing levels of technological development as a result of global trend of increasing economic growth. In order to meet the increasing demand of energy, a significant portion of energy need is supplied through fossil fuel. An increase in CO₂ emissions and the corresponding occurrence of global warming is inevitable through the consumption of fossil fuels such as coal, lignite and petroleum. CO₂ has the greatest impact among greenhouse gasses causing global climate change.

Energy is regarded as one of the fundamental inputs in production process which facilitates economic and social development. However, environmental problems are becoming more apparent especially in developing countries with high rates of energy consumption and a weak association of environmental management with infrastructure. Nonetheless, developing countries have been continuing to increase their production despite adverse impacts on the environment in order to keep costs low. Pollution originating from economic growth and the unsustainability of this effect on the environment have deemed it necessary for countries to utilize clean production technologies. That's why, developed countries have begun switching to environmentally conscious production techniques since 1990s. (Çetintaş et al., 2016).

Various international actions have been undertaken with the intent of finding solutions for environmental problems. "United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)" was signed in 1992 as the possible consequences of global warming began to appear to be the main issue regarding the environment. The aim of the agreement was to ensure to keep the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere at a stabilized level in order to avoid a man-made effect on the climate system. Kyoto Protocol was adopted at the third session of the Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC in December 1997 in Kyoto, Japan. The protocol put developed countries under obligation to limit and decrease greenhouse gas emissions (www.enerji.gov.tr, 2019). Global warming, although dependent on world-wide greenhouse gas emissions especially on CO₂ emission, its consequences vary across countries depending on countries' differences on social and natural properties. From past to present, greenhouse emissions appear to be more prevalent in developed countries. Nonetheless, developing countries which make up 85% of the world population, account for approximately half of all greenhouse gas emission. In this context, the increasing threat of global warming and climate change pose on the environment pulled the attention towards the relationship between economic growth, energy consumption and CO₂ emission (Sancar & Polat, 2018).

There is a growing body of literature on the effect of CO₂ emissions on economic growth. However, there is not any study in this field focusing on the effects of per capita income and high technology export on CO₂ emissions. The contribution of the present study to literature therefore is of high importance for filling a gap in the empirical literature. For this purpose, the present study aims to investigate the effect of per capita income and high technology export on CO₂ emissions in G20 countries, with the exception of Russia due to lack of data availability, for the period of 1992-2014 via panel data analysis. The motivations of this study are the development of the countries around the world and also the reflections of the climate change that become apparent increasingly in our daily lives. This development of countries is observed both in consumption dimension with the increase of per capita income and in production dimension with the increasing production and export volumes of high technology products. At the end of the

analysis, our theoretical expectation is to see a decreasing effect of high technology export on carbon emissions and an increasing effect of income per capita on CO₂ emissions. Within this context, the structure of the present study is organized as follows: Literature review is presented in Section 2, the data and research model is explained in Section 3 and the obtained results are given in Section 4. Limitation of the research is mentioned in the Section 5. Finally, the findings of the study are discussed and evaluated in the Section 6.

2. Literature review

Although studies investigating the relationship between CO₂ emissions, high technology export and economic growth are not very common in empirical literature, there are many studies that investigate the relationship between CO₂ emissions and economic growth, or high technology export and economic growth specifically. Most of these studies indicate significant and positive relationships between both CO₂ emissions and economic growth, and high technology export and economic growth. Within this context, some of these studies exploring the relationship between CO₂ emissions and economic growth, and the relationship between high technology export and economic growth are presented below in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively.

TABLE 1. STUDIES EXAMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CO₂ EMISSION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

STUDIES	PERIOD/COUNTRIES	METHOD	RESULTS
Sarısoy & Yıldız (2006)	1992-2009: 15 developed and 15 developing countries	Panel data analysis	It has been concluded that CO ₂ emission will increase with the increase in income.
Jalil & Mahmud (2009)	1975-2005: China	ARDL model	An inverse U-shaped relationship was found between carbon dioxide emissions and per capita income.
Acaravcı & Öztürk (2010)	1960-2005: 19 european countries	ARDL, Granger causality	One-way causality from GDP to CO ₂ emissions has been identified.
Öztürk & Acaravcı (2010)	1968-2005: Turkey	ARDL boundary test and Granger causality test	According to the results of the study, cointegration relationship was found between the variables. In addition, the increase in CO ₂ emissions has been found to reduce revenue.
Arı & Zeren (2011)	2000-2005: Mediterranean countries	Panel data analysis	CO ₂ emissions increase at high levels of economic growth.
Çınar (2011)	1971-2007: OECD countries	Panel cointegration test	The results of the study show that the level of pollution increases as a result of the increase in income.
Saatçi & Dumrul (2011)	1950-2007: Turkey	Unit root test with structural break and Cointegration test	The presence of inverted U-shape relationship between environmental pollution and economic growth in the turkey has been determined.
Pao & Tsai (2011)	1971-2005: BRIC countries	Panel data ECM	One-way causality from CO ₂ emissions to GDP has been identified.
Shahbaz, Lean & Shabbir (2012)	1971-2009: Pakistan	Granger causality test	A causal relationship was found from economic growth to CO ₂ emissions.
Hamit-Haggar (2012)	1990-2007: Canadian Industrial Sectors	Granger causality test	One-way causality relationship from economic growth to CO ₂ was found.
Apergis & Jebli (2015)	1995-2011: 42 Sub-Saharan African Countries	Panel causality test	It has been determined that there is a one-way causality from real GDP to CO ₂ emission.

TABLE 1. STUDIES EXAMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CO₂ EMISSION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

STUDIES	PERIOD/COUNTRIES	METHOD	RESULTS
Gülmez (2015)	2000-2012: 24 OECD Countries	Panel cointegration and Panel Granger causality	As a result of the analyzes, it was determined that economic growth and air pollution variables had long-term cointegration relationship.
Keskingöz & Karamelikli (2015)	1960-2011: Turkey	ARDL Boundary Testing Approach	According to the test results, the existence of long-term relationship with CO ₂ emission, foreign trade and growth was determined.
Topallı (2016)	1980-2010: India, China, Brazil and South Africa	Panel cointegration and Panel causality test	According to the individual results of the countries, it has been determined that there is a significant increase in CO ₂ emission along with economic growth in these countries.
Ergün & Atay Polat (2017)	1980-2010: G7 Countries	Dumitrescu-Hurlin causality test	The two-way causality relationship between CO ₂ emission and GDP was determined.
Akbulut Bekar (2018)	1977-2014: Turkey	Toda-Yamamoto and Dolado-Lütkepohl VAR causality methods	One-way causality from CO ₂ emissions to GDP has been identified.

Table 1 is comprised of studies investigating the relationship between CO₂ emission and economic growth. Findings of all reviewed studies suggest a significant relationship between CO₂ emissions and economic growth and also reveal that economic growth increases CO₂ emissions in all countries.

TABLE 2. STUDIES ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HIGH TECHNOLOGY EXPORTS AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

STUDIES	PERIOD/COUNTRIES	METHOD	RESULTS
Alam (2003)	1959-1990: (Mexico) 1955-1990: Mexico, Brazil	Time series analysis	The export-based growth hypothesis was rejected in the manufacturing industry.
Wörz (2004)	1981- 1997: OECD Member 45 Countries	Dynamic panel regression analysis	Specialization in industrial export products positively affects economic growth.
Parida & Sahoo (2007)	1980-2002: India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka	Panel data analysis	The findings of the study support the export-led growth hypothesis.
Falk (2009)	1980-2004: 22 OECD countries	GMM panel estimator	It has concluded that there is a high significant relationship between high-tech product exports and economic growth.
Kılavuz & Topcu (2012)	1998-2006: 22 developing countries	Panel data analysis	High-tech manufacturing industry exports had a positive impact on growth.
Göçer (2013)	1996- 2012: 11 Asian Countries	Panel data analysis	A positive correlation was found between R & D's high-tech exports, ICT exports, total exports and economic growth.
Gökmen & Turen (2013)	1995- 2010: 15 EU Member States	Panel causality test and Granger Causality Test	There is a positive relationship between the economic growth of high-tech exports.

TABLE 2. STUDIES ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HIGH TECHNOLOGY EXPORTS AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

STUDIES	PERIOD/COUNTRIES	METHOD	RESULTS
Telatar et al. (2016)	1996/Q1- 2015/ Q3: Türkiye	Engle-Granger co-integration and Granger causality test	Exports of high technology products contribute positively and positively to economic growth.
Ustabaş & Ersin (2016)	1989-2014: Turkey and South Korea	Time series analysis	The impact on economic growth of high-tech exports to South Korea while in a positive direction and positive in the long term, this effect is only valid for a short period for Turkey.
Kabaklarlı et al., (2018)	1989-2015: OECD Countries	Panel data analysis	It is determined that there is a long-term relationship between high technology exports and economic growth in OECD countries.

Table 2 depicts the studies examining the relationship between high technology export and economic growth. All studies indicated significant, positive results with regards to the relationship between high technology export and economic growth.

Recent studies in literature also examine the relationship between advances in science and technology and carbon emission efficiency. Liu et al. (2017), for instance, analyzed carbon emission efficiency for 285 cities in China between 2004 and 2016. The findings of the study suggested that increasing technological expenditure could in turn increase carbon emission efficiency. Wang et al. (2019) conducted a study oriented towards the capacity of decreasing carbon emissions in China at a provincial level covering the years from 1997 to 2014 and discovered that investments of research and development had an impact on decreasing carbon emissions. Zeng et al. (2019) looked into carbon emission efficiency in China covering data from 2005 to 2015. In the study utilizing variables such as the level of foreign trade, utilization of foreign capital, and advances in science and technology, all variables were found to have positive effects on carbon emission.

The present study contributes to the existing literature since there is no study which relates carbon emission with high technology export. Our hypothesis, within this context, is to reveal that there is a distinction among G20 countries in terms of this relationship. Although the countries in G20 community represents the biggest economies of the world in terms of GDP's, they have completely different factor endowements, economic structure, cultural-political features etc. Depending on these differences, we expect to see some differences also in their contribution to carbon emission.

3. Data and research model

In today's world where global warming is becoming a main topic of conversation, awareness surrounding the impacts of countries' economic performances and developmental levels on carbon emissions and environmental degradation is on the rise as well. There are many studies in literature conducted within this context. As presented in the literature review section, most empirically-analyzed studies look either into the

relationship between economic growth and CO₂ emission or the relationship between high technology export and economic growth. That's why, we aim to examine the impact of high technology export of countries on carbon emissions as well as the effect of per capita income. On this purpose, G20 countries, except Russia, were analyzed within the scope of the years 1992 to 2014. Russia was not included in the analysis was due to lack of the data. The reason why the analysis period covers years up to 2014 is because the data for the CO₂ variable is limited only to cover up to 2014.

TABLE 3. EXPLANATIONS ON THE VARIABLES USED

VARIABLES	DESCRIPTION OF THE VARIABLE	SOURCE OF THE DATA
$Log(CO_2)$	Logarithm of CO ₂ emission (metric tons per capita)	World Bank
$Log(HIGH)$	Logarithm of export share of manufacturing sector in high-technology export	World Bank
$Log(PCGDP)$	Logarithm of per capita GDP	World Bank

The variables used in the analysis are given in Table 3. Investigating the trend of the variables within the given period in G20 countries will help us to interpret the findings. In line with this objective, Graph 1 depicts the progress of per capita CO₂ emission in G20 countries.

FIGURE 1. CO₂ EMISSIONS PER CAPITA

Source: Organized using the World Bank data. The trends of the series were obtained by Hodrick-Prescott method.

Figure 1 indicates that per capita CO₂ emissions decrease within the given period in the United States, Canada, Germany, the United Kingdom, Italy and France. These are the developed countries of G20 community. The developing G20 countries, on the other hand, display an increase in CO₂ emission in the given period. Australia appears as an exception among developed countries as it exhibits increase of per capita CO₂ emission although being categorized a developed country.

FIGURE 2. INCOME PER CAPITA

Source: Organized using the World Bank data. The trends of the series were obtained by Hodrick-Prescott method.

As seen in Figure 2, per capita income levels indicates an increase in all countries during the period. It is seen in the graph that there is an apparent distinction between developed and developing countries of G20 with regards to per capita income. The developed countries have higher levels of per income capita compared to the developing countries. An exception to this is Saudi Arabia. Despite being a developing country, per capita income in this oil-rich country ranks second in pursuit of the United States. South Korea, on the other hand, appears to swiftly catch up to developed countries in terms of per capita income.

Figure 3 that depicts the ratio of high technology product export in manufacturing export, indicates a downward trend during the period for the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, Canada and Italy. What these countries have in common is that they are all the developed countries of the G20 community. This downward trend can be explained by the transformation of the production structure from manufacturing industry to service sector in developed economies. On the contrary, the other countries display an upward trend within the given period. South Korea, China and France rank top three with regards to the indicator in question.

FIGURE 3. SHARE OF HIGH-TECH EXPORTS IN MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY EXPORTS

Source: Organized using the World Bank data. The trends of the series were obtained by Hodrick-Prescott method.

We intend to estimate the model below by using these variables:

$$\text{LogCO}_{2it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{1i}\text{LogHIGH}_{it} + \beta_{2i}\text{LogPCGDP}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

As a result of the analysis, we expect to find a positive impact of per capita income on carbon emissions meaning that an increase in per capita income points to an increase in carbon emissions as well. We also expect to see a negative impact of high technology export on carbon emissions, meaning that an increase in the share of high technology export in manufacturing export refers to a decrease in carbon emission. This expectation is in parallel with the findings from the studies examining the relationship between high technology and carbon efficiency, as mentioned in the literature review section.

Prior to the findings of the analyses, descriptive statistics of the variables used are given in Table 4.

As multicollinearity problem may lead to a misestimating of regression coefficients, an expansion of confidence intervals and a shrinkage in t-test values, it is essential to analyze the correlation matrix prior to econometric analysis in order to avoid the this problem. One of various methods of determining whether there is multicollinearity between independent variables is to calculate correlation coefficients. In the case in which the correlation coefficient between variables in its absolute value are close to 1, it is stated that

there is multicollinearity between the given variables (Topal et al., 2010). Table 5 presents the correlation coefficients between variables used in the analysis.

TABLE 4. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

VARIABLES	NUMBER OF OBSERVATIONS	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	MINIMUM	MAXIMUM
<i>Log(CO₂)</i>	414	0.789	0.365	-0.114	1.305
<i>Log(HIGH)</i>	414	1.010	0.449	-1.016	1.545
<i>Log(PCGDP)</i>	414	4.292	0.351	3.267	4.717

TABLE 5. CORRELATION MATRIX

	<i>Log(CO₂)</i>	<i>Log(HIGH)</i>	<i>Log(PCGDP)</i>
<i>Log(CO₂)</i>	1	-	-
<i>Log(HIGH)</i>	0.10	1	-
<i>Log(PCGDP)</i>	0.84	0.09	1

Whereas the correlation between variables *Log(CO₂)* and *Log(HIGH)* is 0.10, this value is 0.84 between *Log(CO₂)* and *Log(PCGDP)*. The correlation coefficient between *Log(PCGDP)* and *Log(HIGH)* is 0.09. The fact that the correlation coefficient between the independent variables *Log(PCGDP)* and *Log(HIGH)* in the model is low suggests that there is no problem of multicollinearity.

First of all, we applied cross-section dependence test to the variables explained in the previous section. Furthermore, MADF test, which is a unit root test compatible with the results of the cross-ecction dependence test was used to examine the stationary of the series. All series were determined to be stationary. Random coefficient panel regression model was estimated based on level values of variables. Random coefficient panel regression model is a regression model that can be applied in the case where coefficients of units differ from one another, that is to say they are not homogeneous. Prior to regression estimation, it is necessary to test for parameter constancy in order to determine whether the units should be represented with common or separate coefficients. In case the parameter stability test proves heterogeneity of the units, coefficients are estimated separately for each unit. Prior to discussing findings obtained from the analysis, it is important to present theoretical information regarding the method summarized.

This is due to the fact that unit root tests used to test stationarity of series differ based on whether cross-sectional dependence is present in series. First generation unit root tests are based upon the assumption that there is no correlation between cross-section units and are used in the case there is no cross-sectional dependence. However, in the case of a correlation between cross-section units, first generation tests have lower strength. For this reason, second generation unit root tests which account for cross-sectional dependence were developed (Yerdelen Tatoğlu, 2013). The first test developed in order to examine the

existence of cross-sectional dependence in series in panel data analysis is the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test developed by Breusch and Pagan. LM test is used when the time dimension of panel data is greater than the cross-sectional dimension ($T > N$). The test statistics ($CDLM_1$) of LM test is as follows (Pesaran, 2004):

$$CDLM_1 = T \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{\rho}_{ij}^2 \quad (1)$$

$\hat{\rho}_{ij}^2$ given in Equation (1) is the estimation of the pairwise correlation of the residuals. Breusch and Pagan indicated that in the case of null hypothesis where no cross sectional dependence presents, $CDLM_1$ test statistics is distributed asymptotically χ^2 . Besides, the applicability of the LM test diminishes in the case of $N \rightarrow \infty$. Following this, Pesaran developed a new test to be used in the case where N and T are of large values. Test statistics of this test ($CDLM_2$) is the scaled version of $CDLM_1$ (Pesaran, 2004):

$$CDLM_2 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N(N-1)}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N (T \hat{\rho}_{ij}^2 - 1) \quad (2)$$

Pesaran et al. later developed a different version of the LM test. Bias-adjusted LM statistics of this test (LM_{adj}) is as follows (Pan et al., 2015):

$$LM_{adj} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}\right)} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{\rho}_{ij} \frac{(T-k)\hat{\rho}_{ij}^2 - \mu_{Tij}}{\sqrt{v_{Tij}^2}} \quad (3)$$

μ_{Tij} and v_{Tij}^2 given in Equation (3) refer to the mean and variance of $(T-k)\hat{\rho}_{ij}^2$ respectively.

Cross-sectional dependence was identified in all series in the present study and thus MADF (Multivariate Aggregated Dickey-Fuller) test, which is a second generation unit root test accounting for cross sectional dependence, was used.

MADF test is a second generation unit root test developed by Taylor and Sarno. Taylor and Sarno have acted upon the equation given in Equation (4) (Taylor & Sarno, 1998):

$$q_{it} = \mu_i + \sum_{j=1}^k \rho_{ij} q_{it-j} + u_{it} \quad (4)$$

In this test, the error term $u_{it} = (u_{1t} \dots \dots u_{Nt})$ is assumed to be independent and normally distributed. Taylor & Sarno have estimated the equation given in Equation (4) based on the fact that the univariate ADF test is rather weak in cases where the root of each autoregressive process of units is close to but different from 1, and taking into consideration the simultaneous correlation between the error terms. Null hypothesis for N equations is expressed as in Equation (5) (Taylor & Sarno, 1998):

$$H_0: \sum_{j=1}^k \rho_{ij} - 1 = 0, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N \quad (5)$$

Wald test statistics obtained as a result of this test is also referred to as MADF statistics. SUR (Seemingly Unrelated Regression) method was used for the estimation of the equation given in Equation (4) (Taylor & Sarno, 1998).

As an alternative to models with fixed coefficient in panel data analysis, the ‘random coefficient model’ which comprises stochastic specification of coefficients for the units was developed. This model allows for the coefficient vector to vary from unit to unit and/or in time (Hsiao & Pesaran, 2004). Following Swamy (1970), random coefficient model is expressed through the matrix notation given in Equation (6) (Poi, 2003):

$$y_i = X_i \beta_i + \epsilon_i \quad (6)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ denotes unit dimension; y_i denotes observation vector in $T_i \times 1$ dimension belongs to the i^{th} unit; X_i denotes non-stochastic variable vector in $T_i \times k$ dimension; β_i denotes the parameter vector in $k \times 1$ dimension specific to the unit i ; ϵ_i is with zero average and $\sigma_{ii} I$ variance. β_i of unit i is related to a common parameter β vector as expressed in Equation (7) (Poi, 2003):

$$\beta_i = \beta + v_i \quad (7)$$

The parameter β_i changes from unit-section to unit-section. In Equation (7), $E(v_i) = 0$ and $E(v_i v_i') = \Sigma$ are equal, and the term v_i is referred to as ‘heterogeneity bias’ (Yerdelen Tatoglu, 2013). Swamy (1970) states that prior to the estimation of the model, it

is necessary to test whether β_i parameter vectors are stationary and are all equal. The null hypothesis to be tested accordingly is as given in Equation (8).

$$H'_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \dots = \beta_n = \beta \quad (8)$$

H'_0 suggests that coefficient vectors are stationary and the investigated units are homogenous. In case this hypothesis is confirmed, then it is accepted that a common relationship for each unit between variables can be estimated. Therefore, in the case the null hypothesis is accepted, it will not be necessary to estimate the random coefficient model. In case H'_0 is rejected, it will not be possible to pool data from each unit in order to estimate a single relationship between variables (Swamy, 1970). Test statistics of the Hausman-type parameter stability test developed by Swamy is expressed as in Equation (9) (Yerdelen Tatoglu, 2013):

$$\chi^2_{k(m-1)} = \sum_{i=1}^m (\hat{\beta}_i - \bar{\beta}^*)' \hat{V}_i^{-1} (\hat{\beta}_i - \bar{\beta}^*) \quad (9)$$

Building upon these explanations regarding econometric methods used in the analysis, findings obtained are presented in the following section of the study.

4. Results

Considering cross-sectional dependence test results given in Table 6, H_0 hypothesis, that implies no cross-sectional dependence, is rejected based on the fact that probability values of test statistics CDLM₁, CDLM₂ and LM_{adj} for each variable is less than 0.05. This result indicates that a cross-sectional dependence is present within the series.

TABLE 6. CROSS-SECTIONAL DEPENDENCE TEST RESULTS

VARIABLES	CDLM 1	CDLM 2	LM ADJ
<i>Log(CO₂)</i>	1424.338 (0.000)	71.649 (0.000)	71.239 (0.000)
<i>Log(HIGH)</i>	730.945 (0.000)	32.010 (0.000)	31.601 (0.000)
<i>Log(PCGDP)</i>	2511.434 (0.000)	133.794 (0.000)	133.385 (0.000)

Test result of the MADF unit-root test is given in Table 7. According to the findings, test statistics are greater than the critical value, meaning that all series are stationary.

TABLE 7. UNIT ROOT TEST RESULTS

VARIABLES	MADF STATISTIC	CRITICAL VALUE (5%)	LAG LENGTH	AIC	BIC
<i>Log(CO₂)</i>	531.53	38.897	3	-2403.3	-2331.61
<i>Log(HIGH)</i>	272.786	41.7	4	-1759.08	-1674.08
<i>Log(PCGDP)</i>	812.299	34.737	1	-3110.82	-3071.54

Note: Maximum lag length is 4, and the appropriate lag length was determined according to the Akaike and Bayesian information criterias.

As the series are stationary, they can be subject to regression analysis with their level values. Before conducting a regression estimate with random coefficients, it is necessary to decide whether the estimation should be made for the average coefficients for the whole panel or for separate coefficients for each country. Results of the parameter constancy test conducted for this purpose and mean coefficient estimations are given in Table 8.

TABLE 8. PARAMETER CONSTANCY TEST RESULT AND AVERAGE COEFFICIENT ESTIMATES

χ^2 test statistics	29694.04 (0.000)
<i>Log(HIGH)</i>	0.05421 (0.270)
<i>Log(PCGDP)</i>	0.472864 (0.001)
Constant	-1.22087 (0.076)

As the probability value for the χ^2 test is less than 0.05, H_0 hypothesis, suggests that coefficients are homogenous, is rejected. In this case, average coefficients are to be ignored and a unit-specific coefficient estimation is required for each country. Country specific coefficient estimations are given in Table 9.

When the results given in Table 9 are analyzed, it is seen that the effect of variable *Log(PCGDP)* on variable *Log(CO₂)* is statistically significant in all analyzed G20 states except for Canada, France and the United States. This significance has a negative value in Germany and the United Kingdom. In other words, CO₂ emissions decrease as per capita income increases. On the contrary, *Log(PCGDP)* has a positive effect on *Log(CO₂)* in Argentina, Australia, Brazil, China, Indonesia, India, Italy, Japan, Korea, Mexico, Saudi Arabia, Turkey and South Africa. This result implies that CO₂ emissions increases when per capita income increases. When coefficients are analyzed, it is seen that Saudi Arabia, Indonesia and Brazil are the three countries where this effect is the highest respectively.

TABLE 9. COUNTRY-SPECIFIC COEFFICIENT ESTIMATES

COUNTRIES	<i>Log(HIGH)</i>	P-VALUE	<i>Log(PCGDP)</i>	P-VALUE
Argentina	0.0589	0.125	0.7479***	0.000
Australia	-0.0552	0.428	0.2299***	0.001
Brazil	0.0767**	0.012	0.9542***	0.000
Canada	0.0489	0.623	0.0401	0.708
China	-0.1801***	0.003	0.8162***	0.000
Germany	0.0044	0.937	-0.6401***	0.000
France	-0.2583***	0.007	-0.2805	0.101
United Kingdom	0.2290***	0.004	-0.4313***	0.001
Indonesia	0.0450	0.376	1.1158***	0.000
India	0.1167*	0.098	0.7153***	0.000
Italy	0.2934***	0.003	0.8089***	0.004
Japan	0.1707***	0.000	0.7618***	0.000
Korea	0.0344	0.626	0.5297***	0.000
Mexican	0.0335	0.429	0.6372***	0.000
Saudi Arabia	-0.0009	0.984	1.2700***	0.000
Turkey	0.0390*	0.059	0.7815***	0.000
USA	0.3092***	0.000	0.0992	0.118
South Africa	0.0106	0.867	0.3559***	0.000

Note: ***, ** and * correspond to 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels, respectively.

The effect of *Log(HIGH)* on *Log(CO₂)* is statistically significant in Brazil, China, France, the United Kingdom, India, Italy, Japan, Turkey and the United States. This effect is negative in China and France while it is positive in other countries. Thus in China and France, per capita carbon emissions decrease as the share of high technology export in manufacturing industry export increases. The opposite is the case for Brazil, the United Kingdom, India, Italy, Japan, Turkey and the United States, i.e., per capita carbon emissions increase in parallel to the share of high technology export in manufacturing industry export. Based on analyzed coefficients, the United States, Italy and the United Kingdom appear to be the countries where this effect is the highest respectively.

5. Limitations of research

We had a limitation in gathering the data for G20 countries. The research covers 18 of G20 countries since the data for Russia is not available for the period of the analysis. Hence, the countries within the context of the research are Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, Germany, France, the United Kingdom, Indonesia, India, Italy, Japan, Korea, Mexico, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, the United States and South Africa.

6. Conclusion and discussion

The present study analyzed the effects of high technology export as well as per capita income on carbon emissions in G20 countries for the period from 1992 to 2014. As seen in the literature review, the overall trend in accordance with the theoretical expectation was an increase in carbon emissions following an increase in per capita income levels. A positive effect was obtained in Argentina, Australia, Brazil, China, Indonesia, India, Italy,

Japan, Korea, Mexico, Saudi Arabia, Turkey and South Africa consistent with the theoretical expectation. In other words, an increase in per capita income in aforementioned countries resulted in an increase in carbon emissions. It is important to notice that all these countries except for Australia, Italy and Japan are developing countries of G20 community. When the coefficient values are considered, it is seen that Saudi Arabia, Brazil and China are the three countries where this effect is highest. Germany and the United Kingdom are the exceptions to this positive correlation between the two variables. These countries exhibit a trend of decreasing per capita CO₂ emission for the analyzed period (Graph 1), although also displaying a trend of increasing per capita income (Graph 2). For Canada, France and the United States, no significant relationship in respect to an effect of per capita income on per capita CO₂ emission was identified

Taking into account the findings regarding the impact of high technology export ratio in manufacturing export on per capita carbon emissions; a positive effect is seen in Brazil, the United Kingdom, India, Italy, Japan, Turkey and the United States. Thus, per capita carbon emissions increase in parallel to increases in the share of export of high technology products. In other words, the increasing ratio of high technology products these countries produce to all manufacturing export does not provide a positive contribution in terms of carbon productivity. However, a negative relationship is the case for China and France. Considering changes in CO₂ emissions (Graph 1) and high technology export (Graph 3) in France, it is seen that while per capita CO₂ emissions are decreasing throughout the analyzed time period, high technology export is on the rise. The statistically significant relationship between the two variables can be evaluated in the manner that the increasing ratio of high technology export in France leads to increasing carbon productivity in the country. Having analyzed these graphs with regards to China; it is seen that despite an increase in China's per capita CO₂ emission; the ratio of high technology export in manufacturing export which had been increasing up until 2008 appears to be on the decline thereafter. The statistically significant relationship between these two variables reveals that China's reduced share of export of high technology products has led to increases in carbon emissions in the country. Taking into consideration that China, "The World's Factory", is the second largest economy and the largest exporter, it is possible to infer that an increase in the ratio of innovative products in the production and export structure of the country is of significant importance in preventing environmental degradation. When coefficients of countries with statistically significant positive relationships are evaluated, it is seen that the United States, Italy, the United Kingdom and Japan have the greatest coefficients, followed by India, Brazil and Turkey. This finding can be summed up to suggest that increases in high technology exports is more influential in increasing CO₂ emissions in developing countries than developed countries.

To sum up the obtained results, it is seen that per capita income has a strong effect on CO₂ emission levels in developing countries whereas exporting of high technology products has a bigger effect on CO₂ emission levels in developed countries. This finding can be interpreted in the way that suggests that developing countries increase their CO₂ emissions through increased income and consumption whereas developed countries do so via production and export.

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